

DEVELOPMENT OF FACIAL MOTORCYCLE GAMES OF THE ETHNIC ETHNICITY FOR K63 STUDENTS NORTHWEST UNIVERSITY

Abstract. Assessing the reality of extracurricular sports and physical training of students K63 Northwestern University and then proposing some measures to contribute to enriching extracurricular activities, preserving the cultural heritage of the students. Northwest Thai ethnic group, thereby improving the quality of extracurricular sports activities of Thai ethnic students studying at the school.

Keywords: Extracurricular sports, folk games, sports games, Thai ethnic games.

1. Question

Northwestern University is located in Son La city in the northwest region of the country, traffic is difficult, and exchange conditions are still limited. With the attention of the Party and State, the school has been training many majors on a wide scale, mainly children of ethnic groups in the Northwest region come here to study.

Every year, on the occasion of the early spring festival, the festival of the season, the festival of the rain, the festival of washing hair, the festival of flowers,... the ethnic minorities in the Northwest organize singing, dancing, Especially, folk games are interested and responded by a large number of people, especially the youth, it has created a healthy and comfortable playground, enhanced exchanges and solidarity, and improved health.. The movement of sports practice and competition has also been strongly developed, especially the sports clubs organized by the school such as table tennis, badminton, football, volleyball clubs, etc. Cloud bridge, martial arts, etc. Although the school and mass organizations have tried to develop the sport movement, especially the exercise movement in sports clubs. However, the folk games of ethnic groups have not been included in extracurricular activities for students to practice. The problem posed here is the need to maintain and widely disseminate the Thai folk mobilization game in Northwestern University, contributing to improving operational efficiency and attracting more students to participate in the game. participate in regular exercise. Stemming from the above issues, we researched the topic: "Development of Thai folk sports games for students of Northwestern

University" through extracurricular sports activities to help them practice. good healthy.

2. Nội dung nghiên cứu

The author researches measures to develop folk sports games of the Thai people in extracurricular sports activities for school students.

Here, we use the following research methods: - Analysis and synthesis of documents; - Investigation of Anket; - Observation of pedagogy; - Interviews and discussions; - Mathematical statistics.

2.1. Game concept [3], [5], [6]

In the Vietnamese Dictionary (1992), the word "game" is understood as a form of entertainment displayed in front of everyone, the word "play" is a common word to refer to activities in leisure time, outside working hours to Entertainment is the main purpose. Since then, games are understood as activities that satisfy human needs, first of all for fun and entertainment.

Folk games are a specific activity only in human society, created by people from real life, handed down through generations and always modified and supplemented to suit each place., from time to time to satisfy the needs of entertainment, cultural exchange and development of the physical and mental aspects of people. Folk movement games are folk games where physical movement and competition are the main ones, comply with the rules of the game and have the distinction of over/under, win/lose, win/lose. That is the premise of the content of national sports activities in Vietnam today. From the perspective of physical education, folk games are one of the effective physical education measures, contributing to building new people to develop comprehensively, meeting the requirements of the renovation cause. country.

2.2. Classification of games

Games in Vietnam have religious significance, including: entertainment games, skillful competition games, sports competition games, and children's games.

2.3. Situation of extracurricular activities of Thai students [3], [5], [6]

2.3.1. Students of Thai ethnic group participate in extracurricular sports activities

Over the years, the school's leaders have paid great attention to physical education and extracurricular sports activities for students such as adding some exercises and activities at the gymnastics club. Sports include: martial arts, table tennis, dance... to help students have opportunities and conditions to improve their health, develop physical fitness and support physical education subjects in the intra-curricular program. Through a survey on the status of Thai students practicing physical training and sports outside the school, the author obtained the following results (see Table 1).

Order	Sport	Sex	Number of people practicing sessions of the day	Number of people practicing on weekdays
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		Male	Female	Bright	Afternoon	Dark	Monday	Tuesday	Wednesday	Thursday	Friday	Saturday	Sunday
1	Badminton	87	39	54	61	16	9	6	8	5	13	22	16
2	Martial Arts	33	54	13	25	34	6	12	6	6	14	32	22
3	Ping pong	12	11	8	17	0	6	11	4	14	10	8	8
4	Volleyball	66	34	67	52	0	14	12	11	6	8	22	16
5	Football	41	28	19	28	14	13	11	8	9	4	12	12
6	Athletics	22	31	18	24	0	8	6	11	12	8	12	10
7	Folk movement game	6	4	21	26	0	2	2	3	6	2	5	2
8	Soccer ball and cloud bridge	34	28	28	33	0	4	12	14	6	13	10	14
9	Not participating in training	15	13	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total		316	242	228	266	64	62	72	65	64	72	123	100

Table 1: Situation of Thai ethnic minority students practicing extracurricular sports at Northwestern University (n = 558)

From the results of Table 1, it can be seen that the total number of Thai students participating in the school's extracurricular sports training is 558 (accounting for 15.23%) compared to the total number of full-time students. 3664. This is a worrying phenomenon for the health maintenance and training of Northwestern University students.

The practice time of the day is relatively equal, mainly in the morning and afternoon.

2.3.2. About the organization of physical training and sports competitions (school year 2022 - 2023)

A year, the school can only organize 13 awards and send athletes to participate in 6 provincial tournaments. While a year, the Ministry of Education and Training and the Vietnam University Sports Association organize dozens of sports tournaments in all subjects that the school does not have a team to participate in. This is also the reason why the school's extracurricular sports movement is not high due to the lack of competition and exchange activities (see Table 2).

Sport	Number of sports tournaments held in the year		Total number of athletes participating
	In schools	Provincial level	
Football	1	0	96
Volleyball	1	1	138
Badminton	1	0	33

Athletics	1	0	59
Soccer ball and cloud bridge	1	0	16
Folk movement game	1	0	34
Total	6	1	376

Table 2: Sports activities in the school year (school year 2022-2023)

The results obtained from Table 2 show that the popular sports are attended by many people such as Football, Volleyball, Rattan Bridge, Badminton... But here we see, students have not participated. abundant and still sparse, uneven. In which, the total number of athletes is 376/3664 students, reaching 10.26%. Thus, the number of students participating in sports competitions is very small compared to the total number of students at the school. Because these are school-level tournaments to recruit the most elite athletes to participate in. The quality of training and competition is not high, so participating in upper-level competitions has not achieved high prizes in terms of number of competitions. competition and performance is still modest.

2.4. Some principles for developing measures to develop folk locomotion games for Thai students. [1], [4], [7]

The basic things are set out on the basis of summarizing experience and scientific analysis of practical activities that must be followed in order to act in a oriented and unified manner. In the field of sports activities, too, the principle is always one of the most important and serious issues to consider in the process of collecting, testing and developing it. Therefore, in order to develop measures to develop folk locomotion games, it is necessary to follow the following principles:

- Combination of inheritance and development.
- Combination of popularization and enhancement in sport development.
- Preserve national identity, respect diversity and actively exchange.
- Combination of national sports and modern sports.

2.5. Proposing measures to develop folk games in extracurricular sports activities for students of Northwestern University [2], [3], [5]

2.5.1. Theoretical basis for building measures

- Preservation and development of folk games is a major policy of the Party and State, which should be thoroughly grasped and promoted to increase the pace of physical training and sport development in line with social development.

- To develop measures to develop folk mobilization games to preserve and promote the culture imbued with national identity, the author is based on the following bases: + The views and guidelines of the Party and State on conservation and development of physical training and sports in general, and folk games in particular; + Decision of the People's Committee of Son La city on conservation and development of folk games; + Based on the actual situation and assessments of folk sports games in combination with consultation with scientists, managers and experts in the sport and physical training industry; + Characteristics

of folk games in the Northwest, practical conditions for conducting a game; + Based on the physical facilities and financial resources, the team of coaches and guides on the organization and management of physical training and sports activities of the province; + Based on the important and great effects of the correct and reasonable measures to contribute to the settlement of the tasks and purposes set out; raise the level of organization, management and operation as well as promote the creativity and effort of thinking and will of those who do the work of organizing and managing; raising the right awareness about the conservation and development of folk games to all school students, helping the practice to become a need and a habit in daily life.

2.5.2. Proposing measures to preserve and develop folk games in extracurricular sports activities

On the basis of theoretical research and assessment of the current situation of folk games in extracurricular sports activities, we propose some specific measures on the conservation and development of folk games. Extra-curricular sports activities include the following measures:

- Strengthen the school's management over the development of folk games.
- Propaganda on the importance of practicing folk games for the physical development of students.
- The Culture, Sports and Tourism industry has a long-term development orientation.
- Regularly send officers in charge to training.
- Organizing regular competitions of folk games at the faculty and school levels and sending athletes to compete at the provincial level.
- Incorporating folk games into regular extracurricular activities program for all faculties.
- Take advantage of local resources and businesses to invest in yards and equipment for students to practice.
- Collecting, adjusting and legalizing folk locomotion games.
- Enhance exchange activities, learn experiences with localities and schools.

2.6. Some folk movement games are collected and put into extracurricular sports activities [3], [5]

In order to ensure the scientific and practicality, the folk locomotion games are included, mainly of the Thai ethnic group, which are highly appreciated by experts and researchers. The following is a specification of the games included in the practice (see table 4).

Nation	Game name	Workout plan				
		Monda y	Tuesda y	Wednesd ay	Thursda y	Frida y
Thai	Toss game	x	x	x		
	Stick pushing game			x	x	x
	Game tug	x	x		x	

The game of tortoises	x	x	x	x	x
Spin game	x	x			x

Table 4: Distribution of time for extra-curricular practice of folk games during the week

Toss game Stick pushing game

Game tugThe game of tortoises

Spin game

3. Conclude

Folk games are a cultural and spiritual activity of the Vietnamese nation. Games in each country and ethnic group are bold with unique cultural features that show the identity of that nation. The game is an important part of the

traditional festivals of the Thai ethnic group in the Northwest. Along with preserving and developing the culture of the ethnic groups in Vietnam, through extracurricular sports activities with healthy cultural contents, folk games are used as a means of physical education., and at the same time contribute to preserving and developing the unique cultural features of the ethnic groups in the Northwest region.

Folk games of Thai ethnic groups are very diverse and rich. Through the research process, we have collected 5 folk games of the Thai ethnic group, including: To mortar, tossing ball, spinning, shooting crossbow, and tosem fast.

In order for the measures to be effective in practice, we need to carry out synchronously. Here, we have focused on collecting, correcting and legalizing the 5 games mentioned above and recommending to put them into extracurricular sports activities for students.

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